

THE PROCEDURAL SIGNIFICANCE OF SPECIALIST PARTICIPATION IN CRIMINAL PROCEEDINGS

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In criminal proceedings, establishing proof encompasses collecting, verifying and evaluating evidence. Various opinions and considerations continue to be expressed regarding the content and essence of the proof process [1, p.25].

In particular, legal scholar G.Z. Tulaganova expressed that proof is understood as the activity of subjects, based on criminal procedural law, to collect, document, verify, and evaluate any information relevant to a specific criminal case in a procedural manner, as well as to confirm the existence of this information on behalf of the state [2, p.141]. We can agree with the opinion expressed by G.Z. Tulaganova. This is because the process of exposing and proving a crime must be based on criminal procedural law.

According to legal scholar O.M. Madaliev, proof is an activity carried out in a procedural manner prescribed by law, performed by investigative bodies, investigators, prosecutors, and courts with the participation of other subjects of proof, to collect, verify and evaluate evidence to establish the truth in a criminal case and solve all tasks of criminal proceedings [3, p.13]. In agreement with O.M. Madaliev's opinion, it is appropriate to acknowledge that the process of proof is not limited only to the circle of persons carrying it out, but is also carried out by other participants directly involved in these processes.

B.A. Azizkhodzhaev expressed that proof consists of advancing investigative hypotheses and their dynamic development, collecting evidence for each hypothesis, studying (verifying) the collected evidence, evaluating it, and making substantiated procedural decisions on the case [4, p.16]. The opinions expressed by B.A. Azizkhodzhaev are somewhat debatable. This is because evidence related to an investigative hypothesis may not be recognized as evidence in the future and may not be significant in the proof process. That is, the proof process must correspond to the truth, be verified, and evaluated in the manner prescribed by law.

D.M. Mirazov notes that in the process of proof, it is necessary to ensure a thorough, comprehensive, complete, and objective examination of all

circumstances to be proven in the case, to ensure respect for the honor and dignity of the persons participating in the case, and to organize the protection of the rights and freedoms of citizens participating in the criminal process [5, p.73]. We can agree with this opinion. This is because the proof process requires persons carrying it out or involved in it to pay attention to circumstances that need to be proven carefully, through comprehensive, complete, and objective examination, while performing their assigned duties.

According to B.T. Bezlepkin, proof should not be limited only to mental activity because it is more about law enforcement, aimed at establishing circumstances significant for the case, and ends with the justification of the final decision on the criminal case [6, pp.75-95].

According to L.A. Tatarov, proof should be understood as purposeful activity to logically substantiate the guilt (or innocence) of the accused (defendant) in committing a crime using evidence collected in the manner prescribed by criminal procedural law [7, p.9].

In agreement with the opinions expressed by B.T. Bezlepkin and L.A. Tatarov, the actions of a person who has committed a socially dangerous act must be proven in cases stipulated by law. Of course, the process of proof is carried out through the application of law, and deviating from the law may be considered going beyond the limits of proof.

B.A. Rajabov has included the identification and use of evidence, along with the collection, verification, and evaluation of evidence, as stages of proof [8, p.23].

We can agree with Professor B.A. Rajabov's opinions. This is because in the process of proof, evidence is first identified and can then be used. It is impossible to achieve the goal of proof without using the evidence obtained in the proof process.

In our opinion, proof is a system of activities of subjects who carry out, participate in, or are involved in proof, for the purpose of identifying, collecting, verifying, evaluating, and using evidence in fulfilling the tasks specified in criminal procedural law.

Proof is carried out through evidence [9, p.10], where the identification of evidence occurs in the form of preliminary examination, and in conducting it, the need to use special knowledge often arises. The participation of a specialist in proof serves as an example of using special knowledge and is mainly manifested in identifying, collecting, and verifying evidence. Identifying and collecting evidence is mainly carried out in pre-trial proceedings.

Analysis of investigative practice shows that in certain situations (when reviewing document circulation, technological processes, etc.), it is necessary to involve a specialist in the preliminary examination. Information obtained with the help of a specialist often contains necessary information indicating the presence or absence of criminal elements, which allows for making correct procedural decisions based on the results of the preliminary examination.

In the pre-trial stage of criminal proceedings, in accordance with the requirements of the Criminal Procedure Code, a specialist may be involved to assist the investigator or inquiry officer in finding, recording, and seizing objects and documents, examining the scene of the incident, and examining the corpse using technical means.

During the examination of the scene of the incident, the specialist provides technical and advisory assistance to the investigator, which helps to conduct the pre-investigation check more quickly and efficiently, to formulate a more accurate description of traces and marks for recording in the protocol, and to identify the probable mechanism of trace formation in connection with the criminal event. During the examination of the scene of an accident, the specialist provides technical assistance in solving special issues. Legal scholar Sh.Kh. Inomjonov notes that operational information available in material compounds is obtained directly by the operational officer or with the help of a specialist [10, p.89]. The specialist provides advice and explanations, as well as identifies the names and functions of certain objects, provides technical assistance in collecting and seizing traces, objects, and other items, which is recorded in the protocol. According to A.Kh. Imomnazarov, in some cases, the failure to involve specialists in examining the scene of an incident in practice is recognized as a permissible error [11, pp.20-21].

We can agree with the opinions expressed by Sh.Kh. Inomjonov and A.Kh. Imomnazarov. In our opinion, in cases where a specialist should participate, failure to ensure their participation may lead to unreliable, poor-quality evidence being collected in the future.

In this regard, the results of a survey conducted among field specialists during the research also confirm the stated opinions.

During the survey, to the question “what role does the participation of a specialist in criminal proceedings play in making decisions on the case?” 90,07 percent of respondents answered “it affects making a well-founded and lawful decision”, 5,96 percent answered “it has no role”, 6,32 percent answered “the participation of a specialist is necessary for formality in the case”, and

93,32 percent answered “it serves to collect significant, reliable, and acceptable evidence for the case, as well as to ensure impartial proceedings” [12]. As can be seen from the survey results, the participation of a specialist in criminal proceedings is very important.

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